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N-Cubic Picture Fuzzy Linear Spaces

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Abstract

Objectives: The major objective of the present work is to apply the concept of N-cubic structure to N-Picture Fuzzy Linear Spaces. It also examines the fundamental operations such as P-union, P-intersection, R-union and R-intersection of N-Cubic Picture Fuzzy Linear Spaces, ENCPFLS and INCPFLS, and discusses in detail both of them with examples. **Methods:** We define P(R)-union and P(R)- intersection of N- Cubic Picture Fuzzy Linear Spaces and its properties by giving few examples with the motivation of the notion of Cubic Picture Fuzzy Linear Space (CPFLS). **Findings:** The notion of external and internal N-Cubic Picture Fuzzy Linear Spaces including their properties are derived. **Novelty:** For the first time, we present the idea of N-Cubic Picture Fuzzy Linear Spaces (NCPFLS), which has been developed on the basis of interval valued N- Picture fuzzy linear spaces (IVNPFLS) and N-Picture fuzzy linear spaces (NPFLS). In addition, we have studied the basic operations which includes P(R)-union and P(R)- intersection on ENCPFLS and INCPFLS.

Keywords: N-picture fuzzy set; N-cubic set; N-Picture fuzzy linear space; Interval valued N-Picture fuzzy linear spaces; P(R) union; P(R)intersection
AMS Subject Classification: 08A72; 03E72

1 Introduction

Based on the development of Zadeh fuzzy set theory 1965⁽¹⁾, Atanassov⁽²⁾ proposed the idea of intuitionistic fuzzy sets, which permit a progressive evaluation of each element in a set. Applications of fuzzy set theory could be tremendous in a variety of fields, including group theory, analysis and topology etc. The theory known as the intuitionistic fuzzy set is intriguing because it includes both membership and non-membership of an element provided that neither one exceeds one. However, it is unable to handle neutral conditions because human nature is prone to disobedience and abstinence. It has been expanded even further to include Picture Fuzzy Sets⁽³⁾, which are widely utilized in decision-making environments including voting, financial accounting and risk assessment in business etc.

Cubic set theory is a further development of fuzzy set theory that was presented by Jun et al.⁽⁴⁾ in 2010 and investigated various properties of cubic set. Cubic picture fuzzy sets are a new notion that emerged from the extension of the cubic set framework⁽⁵⁾. In

numerous physical problems, cubic sets overlook the negative characteristics of a given thing and solely assess its positive aspects. Further, the fuzzy set concept is expanded to interval valued intuitionistic fuzzy set by Liu et al. (2020) ⁽⁶⁾ and used in Multicriteria Decision Making Problems and a new function known as the negative valued function which is introduced and considered N-structures ⁽⁷⁾. In addition, they investigated for related problems by using N-structure theory to BCK/BCI algebra and subtraction algebra. The idea of N-Cubic sets, which are the combination of an N-fuzzy set on the domain [-1, 0] and an interval valued N-fuzzy set, was first proposed by Y.B. Jun and others ⁽⁸⁾.

The concepts of fuzzy field and fuzzy linear space were first presented by Nanda ⁽⁹⁾. Afterwards, Gu Wexiang and Lu ⁽¹⁰⁾ provided some basic features and redefined the terms fuzzy field and fuzzy linear space. Vijaybalaji et al. ⁽¹¹⁾ further developed the theory to cubic linear space. The notion of N-cubic linear spaces, which combine IVNFLS and NFLS, was proposed by P. R. Kavyasree and B. Surender Reddy and their characteristics described in ⁽¹²⁾. Cubic picture fuzzy linear space and Cubic Pythagorean fuzzy linear space were also introduced by the same research group and examined their properties ⁽¹³⁻¹⁵⁾.

In the present research work, we introduce the idea of N-Cubic Picture Fuzzy Linear Spaces. We propose the notions of P-union, P-intersection, R-union and R-intersection of N-Cubic Picture Fuzzy Linear Spaces. We showed that N-Cubic Picture Fuzzy Linear Spaces is satisfied with respect to R-intersection. Using counterexamples, it is demonstrated that two N-Cubic Picture Fuzzy Linear Spaces do not necessarily have to be N-Cubic Picture Fuzzy Linear Spaces for R-union, P-union, and P-intersection to exist. The notion of internal and external N-Cubic Picture Fuzzy Linear Spaces is presented. It is proved that the R-intersection of two N-cubic picture fuzzy linear spaces representing internal (or external) is also an internal (or external) N-Cubic picture fuzzy linear spaces. We presented an example to demonstrate that the P-union, R-union and P-intersection of two internal (resp. external) NCPFLSP are not internal (resp. external) NCPFLSP.

2 Methodology

Definition 2.1 :

An N interval number is a closed sub interval of [-1,0] and the collection of all closed sub-intervals of [-1,0] is represented by $\tilde{D}[-1,0]$. It is of the form $\tilde{D}[-1,0] = \{\hat{e} = [e^-, e^+] : e^- \leq e^+, e^-, e^+ \in [-1,0]\}$. Notably, the operations " \geq ", " \leq ", " $=$ ", " \max ", " \min " are defined as follows

- i) $\hat{e}_1 \geq \hat{e}_2$ if and only if $e_1^- \geq e_2^-$ and $e_1^+ \geq e_2^+$
- ii) $\hat{e}_1 \leq \hat{e}_2$ if and only if $e_1^- \leq e_2^-$ and $e_1^+ \leq e_2^+$
- iii) $\hat{e}_1 = \hat{e}_2$ if and only if $e_1^- = e_2^-$ and $e_1^+ = e_2^+$
- iv) $\max\{\hat{e}_1, \hat{e}_2\} = [\max\{e_1^-, e_2^-\}, \max\{e_1^+, e_2^+\}]$
- v) $\min\{\hat{e}_1, \hat{e}_2\} = [\min\{e_1^-, e_2^-\}, \min\{e_1^+, e_2^+\}]$

Definition 2.2 :

For an N interval number $\hat{e}_s \in \tilde{D}[-1,0]$, where $s \in \Delta$ we define $\inf_{s \in \Delta} \hat{e}_s = [\inf_{s \in \Delta} \hat{e}_s^-, \inf_{s \in \Delta} \hat{e}_s^+]$ and $\sup_{s \in \Delta} \hat{e}_s = [\sup_{s \in \Delta} \hat{e}_s^-, \sup_{s \in \Delta} \hat{e}_s^+]$

Definition 2.3 :

Let S be a non-empty set. A Picture Fuzzy set in S is defined as

$PF = \{(S, P_j(s), L_j(s), N_j(s) : s \in S)\}$ where $P_j : S \rightarrow (0, 1)$, $L_j : S \rightarrow (0, 1)$, $N_j : S \rightarrow (0, 1)$ are said to be the positive, neutral and negative membership degrees of s in S respectively and P_j, L_j, N_j are satisfies the following conditions that $P_j(s) + L_j(s) + N_j(s) \leq 1 \forall s \in S$.

Now the refusal membership of s in S could be

$$R_j(s) = 1 - (P_j(s) + L_j(s) + N_j(s)) \forall s \in S.$$

Definition 2.4 :

Let S be a non-empty set. An Interval Valued Picture Fuzzy Set (IVPFS) in S is defined as $I_{PF} = \{(S, I_{P_j}(s), I_{L_j}(s), I_{N_j}(s) : s \in S)\}$,

where $I_{P_j} : S \rightarrow \tilde{D}(0, 1)$, $I_{L_j} : S \rightarrow \tilde{D}(0, 1)$, $I_{N_j} : S \rightarrow \tilde{D}(0, 1)$ are said to be degree of the positive, neutral and negative membership degrees of s in S respectively. Also, $I_{P_j}, I_{L_j}, I_{N_j}$ in turn satisfies the following condition that

$$0 \leq \sup(I_{P_j}(s)) + \sup(I_{L_j}(s)) + \sup(I_{N_j}(s)) \leq 1 \forall s \in S.$$

Definition 2.5 :

Let S be a non-empty set. The Cubic Picture Fuzzy set in S can be defined as $PF^C = \{(s, I_{PF^C}(s), K_{PF^C}(s) : s \in S)\}$ and it is briefly denoted by $PF^C = (I_{PF^C}, K_{PF^C})$. In which

$I_{PF^C}(s) = (s, I_{P_j^c}(s), I_{L_j^c}(s), I_{N_j^c}(s)) : s \in S$ is an interval valued picture fuzzy set in S and $R_{PF^C}(s) = \{(S, P_j(s), L_j(s), N_j(s) : s \in S)\}$ is a picture fuzzy set in S.

Definition 2.6 :

Let T be a non-empty set. A N-Picture Fuzzy Set in T is defined as

$R_{PF}^N = \{(t, U_i(t), V_i(t), W_i(t) : t \in T)\}$ where $U_i : T \rightarrow (-1, 0), V_i : T \rightarrow (-1, 0), W_i : T \rightarrow (-1, 0)$

be the positive, neutral and negative membership degrees of t in T respectively. U_i, V_i, W_i are satisfies the following condition that $U_i(t) + V_i(t) + W_i(t) \leq 0$. Now the degrees of refusal membership of t in T can be $O_j(s) = 1 - (U_i(t) + V_i(t) + W_i(t)) \forall t \in T$.

Definition 2.7 :

Let T be a non-empty set. An Interval Valued N-Picture Fuzzy set in T can be defined as $J_{PF}^N = \{(t, J_{U_i}(t), J_{V_i}(t), J_{W_i}(t) : t \in T)\}$, where $J_{U_i} : T \rightarrow \bar{D}(-1, 0), J_{V_i} : T \rightarrow \bar{D}(-1, 0), J_{W_i} : T \rightarrow \bar{D}(-1, 0)$ are said to be the degrees of positive, neutral and negative membership of t in T respectively and $J_{U_i}(t), J_{V_i}(t), J_{W_i}(t)$ are satisfies the following conditions $-1 \leq sup(J_{U_i}(t)) + sup(J_{V_i}(t)) + sup(J_{W_i}(t)) \leq 0 \forall t \in T$.

Definition 2.8 :

Let T be a non-empty set. A N-Cubic picture fuzzy set in T can be defined as

$C_{PF}^N = \{t, J_{PF}^N(t), R_{PF}^N(t) : t \in T\}$. It is briefly denoted by $C_{PF}^N = (J_{PF}^N, R_{PF}^N)$ in that

$J_{PF}^N(t) = \{(t, J_{U_i}(t), J_{V_i}(t), J_{W_i}(t) : t \in T)\}$ is an interval valued N-Picture fuzzy set in T and

$R_{PF}^N(t) = \{(t, U_i(t), V_i(t), W_i(t) : t \in T)\}$ is a N-Picture fuzzy set in T.

Definition 2.9 :

For any $C_{PF_i}^N = \{t, J_{PF_i}^N(t), R_{PF_i}^N(t) \setminus t \in T\}$ where $i \in \Delta$ and Δ is an indexed set. Now we define

- i) $\cup_{i \in \Delta^P} C_{PF_i}^N = \{< t, \cap_{i \in \Delta} J_{PF_i}^N(t), \cap_{i \in \Delta} R_{PF_i}^N(t) \setminus t \in T >\}$ (P-union)
- ii) $\cap_{i \in \Delta^P} C_{PF_i}^N = \{< t, \cup_{i \in \Delta} J_{PF_i}^N(t), \cup_{i \in \Delta} R_{PF_i}^N(t) \setminus t \in T >\}$ (P-intersection)
- iii) $\cup_{i \in \Delta^R} C_{PF_i}^N = \{< t, \cap_{i \in \Delta} J_{PF_i}^N(t), \cup_{i \in \Delta} R_{PF_i}^N(t) \setminus t \in T >\}$ (R-union)
- iv) $\cap_{i \in \Delta^R} C_{PF_i}^N = \{< t, \cup_{i \in \Delta} J_{PF_i}^N(t), \cap_{i \in \Delta} R_{PF_i}^N(t) \setminus t \in T >\}$ (R-intersection)

3 Results and discussion

N-Cubic Picture Fuzzy Linear Spaces

Definition 3.1 :

For a linear space \mathcal{L} over a field F be a N-Cubic Picture Fuzzy set,

$R_{PF}^N = (U_i(t), V_i(t), W_i(t))$ is said to be a N-Picture Fuzzy Linear space

$\mathcal{L}_{PF}^N = \{(\mathcal{L}, U_i, V_i, W_i)\}$ where $U_i : \mathcal{L} \rightarrow [-1, 0], V_i : \mathcal{L} \rightarrow [-1, 0],$ and $W_i : \mathcal{L} \rightarrow [-1, 0]$ and also satisfies the following conditions

$\mathcal{L}_{PF}^N(\xi a * \delta b * \rho c) \geq \mathcal{L}_{PF}^N(a) \cap \mathcal{L}_{PF}^N(b) \cap \mathcal{L}_{PF}^N(c)$. For any $\xi, \delta, \rho \in F$ and a, b, c $\in \mathcal{L}$.

Definition 3.2 :

An interval valued N-Picture fuzzy set $J_{PF}^N(t) = \{(t, J_{U_i}(t), J_{V_i}(t), J_{W_i}(t) : t \in T)\}$ is said to be an interval valued N-Picture Fuzzy linear space it is denoted by $\mathcal{L}_{IPF}^N = (\mathcal{L}, J_{U_i}, J_{V_i}, J_{W_i})$ over the field F if the following conditions satisfied

$\mathcal{L}_{IPF}^N(\xi a * \delta b * \rho c) \leq max\{\mathcal{L}_{IPF}^N(a), \mathcal{L}_{IPF}^N(b), \mathcal{L}_{IPF}^N(c)\}$ for any $\xi, \delta, \rho \in F$ and a, b, c $\in \mathcal{L}$.

Definition 3.3 :

Let \mathcal{L} be a linear space over a field F, \mathcal{L}_{IPF}^N is an interval valued N-Picture fuzzy linear space and \mathcal{L}_{PF}^N is a Picture Fuzzy linear space. A N-Cubic Picture Fuzzy set $C_{PF}^N = (J_{PF}^N, R_{PF}^N)$ is said to be Cubic Picture Fuzzy linear space of \mathcal{L} if

- i) $J_{PF}^N(\xi a * \delta b * \rho c) \leq max\{J_{PF}^N(a), J_{PF}^N(b), J_{PF}^N(c)\}$
- ii) $R_{PF}^N(\xi a * \delta b * \rho c) \geq min\{R_{PF}^N(a), R_{PF}^N(b), R_{PF}^N(c)\}$ for all $\xi, \delta, \rho \in F$ and a, b, c $\in \mathcal{L}$.

Example 3.1 : Now, we consider a numerical example for N-Cubic Picture fuzzy set. Let ‘S’ be a non-empty universal set. Consider the values given in the below mentioned Table 1.

Table 1. Values pertaining to interval valued N-Picture fuzzy set (IVNPF) J_{PF}^N and N-Picture fuzzy set (NPFS)

S	J_{PF}^N	R_{PF}^N
s_1	[-0.3, -0.2], [-0.25, -0.15], [-0.39, -0.31]	[-0.4, -0.08, -0.06]
s_2	[-0.54, -0.45], [-0.25, -0.23], [-0.43, -0.20]	[-0.31, -0.27, -0.01]
s_3	[-0.17, -0.3], [-0.36, -0.24], [-0.23, -0.11]	[-0.2, -0.06, -0.10]

Here J_{PF}^N is an interval valued N- Picture fuzzy set and R_{PF}^N is a N-Picture fuzzy set of S over the field F . The values given in the table 1 are placed in the matrix over field F and it can be referred to decision matrix commonly utilized in decision making problems solving methods. Further, the above said example satisfied the conditions needed for the Cubic Picture fuzzy set $C_{PF}^N = (J_{PF}^N, R_{PF}^N)$ to be a Cubic Picture fuzzy linear space.

Definition 3.4 :

Let $J_{PF_1}^N = (J_{U_1}, J_{V_1}, J_{W_1})$ and Let $J_{PF_2}^N = (J_{U_2}, J_{V_2}, J_{W_2})$ are two interval valued N-Cubic Picture fuzzy linear spaces then their union and intersection can be defined as

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m) = \min \{ J_{PF_1}^N(m), J_{PF_2}^N(m) \}$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m) = \max \{ J_{PF_1}^N(m), J_{PF_2}^N(m) \} \text{ for } m \in \mathcal{L}.$$

Definition 3.5 :

Let $R_{PF_1}^N = \{(U_i, V_i, W_i)\}$ and Let $R_{PF_2}^N = \{(U_i, V_i, W_i)\}$ are two N-Cubic Picture fuzzy linear spaces then their union and intersection can be defined as

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)(m) = \min \{ R_{PF_1}^N(m), R_{PF_2}^N(m) \}$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m) = \max \{ R_{PF_1}^N(m), R_{PF_2}^N(m) \} \text{ for } m \in \mathcal{L}$$

Theorem 3.1 : Let $C_{PF_1}^N = (J_{PF_1}^N, R_{PF_1}^N)$ and $C_{PF_2}^N = (J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_2}^N)$ are two N-Cubic Picture fuzzy linear spaces then their R-intersection $(C_{PF_1}^N \cap C_{PF_2}^N)_R = (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)$ is again N-Cubic Picture fuzzy linear space.

Proof. We have $(J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m) = \max \{ J_{PF_1}^N(m), J_{PF_2}^N(m) \}$.

Consider $(J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3) = \max \{ J_{PF_1}^N(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3), J_{PF_2}^N(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3) \}$ for any $\xi, \delta, \rho \in F$ and $a, b, c \in \mathcal{L}$. From definition 3.3

$$\begin{aligned} & (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3) \leq \max \{ \max \{ J_{PF_1}^N(m_1), J_{PF_1}^N(m_2), J_{PF_1}^N(m_3) \}, \\ & \max \{ J_{PF_2}^N(m_1), J_{PF_2}^N(m_2), J_{PF_2}^N(m_3) \} \\ & = \max \{ \max \{ J_{PF_1}^N(m_1), J_{PF_1}^N(m_2), J_{PF_1}^N(m_3) \}, \max \{ J_{PF_2}^N(m_1), J_{PF_2}^N(m_2), J_{PF_2}^N(m_3) \} \\ & = \max \{ \max \{ J_{PF_1}^N(m_1), J_{PF_2}^N(m_1) \}, \max \{ J_{PF_1}^N(m_2), J_{PF_2}^N(m_2) \}, \max \{ J_{PF_1}^N(m_3), J_{PF_2}^N(m_3) \} \\ & = \max \{ (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1), (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2), (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) \} \end{aligned}$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3) \leq \max \{ (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1), (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2), (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) \} \quad (3.1)$$

Hence, $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} J_{PF_i}^N$ is an interval valued N-Picture fuzzy linear space.

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)(m) = \min \{ R_{PF_1}^N(m), R_{PF_2}^N(m) \} \text{ for } m \in \mathcal{L}.$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3) = \min \{ R_{PF_1}^N(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3), R_{PF_2}^N(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3) \}$$

From definition 3.3 we have

$$\begin{aligned} & (R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3) \geq \min \{ \min \{ R_{PF_1}^N(m_1), R_{PF_1}^N(m_2), R_{PF_1}^N(m_3) \}, \\ & \min \{ R_{PF_2}^N(m_1), R_{PF_2}^N(m_2), R_{PF_2}^N(m_3) \} \\ & = \min \{ \min \{ R_{PF_1}^N(m_1), R_{PF_1}^N(m_2), R_{PF_1}^N(m_3) \}, \min \{ R_{PF_2}^N(m_1), R_{PF_2}^N(m_2), R_{PF_2}^N(m_3) \} \\ & = \min \{ \min \{ R_{PF_1}^N(m_1), R_{PF_2}^N(m_1) \}, \min \{ R_{PF_1}^N(m_2), R_{PF_2}^N(m_2) \}, \min \{ R_{PF_1}^N(m_3), R_{PF_2}^N(m_3) \} \\ & = \min \{ (R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1), (R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_2), (R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) \} \end{aligned}$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3) \geq \min \{ (R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1), (R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_2), (R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) \} \quad (3.2)$$

Hence, $\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} R_{PF_i}^N$ is an N-Picture fuzzy linear space.

Therefore, as per Equations (3.1) and (3.2) the conditions needed for R-intersection to be N-Picture Fuzzy linear space are satisfied.

Remark 3.1 : By using an example, we show that the intersection of two intervals valued N-Picture fuzzy linear spaces does not necessarily have to be interval valued N-Picture fuzzy linear space and does not have to satisfy the first condition of N-Cubic Picture fuzzy linear space as specified in definition 3.3.

Example 3.2 : Let us consider a linear space \mathcal{L} over a field F and the binary operation $*$ on \mathcal{L} can be defined as $m_1 = m_2 * m_3$ and $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$. Consider interval valued N-Picture fuzzy sets and N-Picture fuzzy sets tabulated below Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2. Values corresponding to IVNPFS(J_{PF}^N) and NPFS (R_{PF}^N)

\mathcal{L}	J_{PF}^N	R_{PF}^N
m_1	[-0.06, -0.04], [-0.29, -0.18], [-0.08, -0.03]	(-0.54, -0.34, -0.22)
m_2	[-0.04, -0.03], [-0.26, -0.17], [-0.28, -0.19]	(-0.19, -0.26, -0.33)
m_3	[-0.17, -0.4], [-0.46, -0.34], [-0.07, -0.03]	(-0.18, -0.16, -0.10)

Table 3. Values for IVNPFS (J_{PF}^N) and NPFS (R_{PF}^N)

\mathcal{L}	J_{PF}^N	R_{PF}^N
m_1	[-0.08, -0.06], [-0.36, -0.24] [-0.16, -0.04]	(-0.61, -0.44, -0.29)
m_2	[-0.15, -0.13], [-0.15, -0.08], [-0.05, -0.02]	(-0.47, -0.31, -0.25)
m_3	[-0.06, -0.03], [-0.06, -0.05], [-0.17, -0.12]	(-0.66, -0.46, -0.21)

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = ([-0.08, -0.06], [-0.36, -0.24] [-0.16, -0.04])$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2) = ([-0.15, -0.13], [-0.26, -0.17] [-0.28, -0.19])$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) = ([-0.17, -0.04], [-0.46, -0.34] [-0.17, -0.12])$$

We have $J_{IPF_1}^N \cap J_{IPF_2}^N$ is an interval valued N-picture fuzzy set in \mathcal{L}

For $m_1 = m_2 * m_3$ and $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$ in definition 3.3

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2 * m_3) \leq \max\{(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2), (J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2)\}$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) \leq \max\{(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2), (J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2)\}$$

$$\leq \max\{([-0.15, -0.13], [-0.26, -0.17] [-0.28, -0.19]),$$

$$([-0.17, -0.04], [-0.46, -0.34], [-0.17, -0.12])\}$$

$$\leq ([-0.15, -0.13], [-0.26, -0.17], [-0.17, -0.12])$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = ([-0.08, -0.06], [-0.36, -0.24], [-0.16, -0.04])$$

$$\leq ([-0.15, -0.13], [-0.26, -0.17], [-0.17, -0.12])$$

Since $[-0.08, -0.06] \leq [-0.15, -0.13]$,

$[-0.36, -0.24] \leq [-0.26, -0.17]$ and $[-0.16, -0.04] \leq [-0.17, -0.12]$ which is inappropriate.

It is clear from the above said example that the intersection of two interval valued N-Picture fuzzy linear space (IVNPFLS) need not be interval valued N-Picture fuzzy linear space (IVNPFLS).

Remark 3.1 : We have provided an example in order to prove that the union of two N-Picture fuzzy linear space need not be N-Picture fuzzy linear space and need not satisfy the second condition of N-Cubic Picture fuzzy linear space (NCPFLS) as defined in definition 3.3.

Example 3.3 : Consider two N-Picture fuzzy set as in Table 2 and Table 3.

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = (-0.54, -0.34, -0.22)$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_2) = (-0.19, -0.26, -0.25)$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) = (-0.18, -0.16, -0.10)$$

We note that $(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)$ is N-Picture fuzzy set in \mathcal{L}

For $m_1 = m_2 * m_3$ and $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$ in definition 3.3

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_2 * m_3) \geq \min \{ R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N(m_2), R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N(m_3) \}$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) \geq \min \{ R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N(m_2), R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N(m_3) \}$$

$$\geq \min \{ (-0.19, -0.26, -0.25), (-0.18, -0.16, -0.10) \}$$

$$\geq (-0.19, -0.26, -0.25)$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = (-0.54, -0.34, -0.22) \geq (-0.19, -0.26, -0.25) \text{ it is incorrect}$$

It is evident from the above example that the union of N-Picture fuzzy linear space need not be N-Picture fuzzy linear space.

Lemma 3.1 : The following conclusions can be drawn from the aforementioned theorem and examples.

i) $C_{PF_1}^N = (J_{PF_1}^N, R_{PF_1}^N)$ and $C_{PF_2}^N = (J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_2}^N)$ are two N-Cubic Picture fuzzy linear spaces then their R-union $(C_{PF_1}^N \cup C_{PF_2}^N)_R = (J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)$ need not be N-Cubic Picture fuzzy linear space.

ii) $C_{PF_1}^N = (J_{PF_1}^N, R_{PF_1}^N)$ and $C_{PF_2}^N = (J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_2}^N)$ are two N-Cubic Picture fuzzy linear spaces then their P-union $(C_{PF_1}^N \cup C_{PF_2}^N)_P = (J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)$ need not be N-Cubic Picture fuzzy linear space.

iii) $C_{PF_1}^N = (J_{PF_1}^N, R_{PF_1}^N)$ and $C_{PF_2}^N = (J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_2}^N)$ are two N-Cubic Picture fuzzy linear spaces then their P-intersection $(C_{PF_1}^N \cap C_{PF_2}^N)_P = (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)$ need not be N-Cubic Picture fuzzy linear space.

Proof . According to example 3.2 and 3.3, it can be observed that R-union is not a N-Cubic Picture fuzzy linear space

i) Consider N-Picture fuzzy linear spaces as Tables 2 and 3 and consider the intersection of N-Picture fuzzy linear spaces we have

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = (-0.61, -0.44, -0.29)$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)(m_2) = (-0.47, -0.31, -0.33)$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) = (-0.66, -0.46, -0.21)$$

For $m_1 = m_2 * m_3$ and $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$ in definition 3.3

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)(m_2 * m_3) \geq \min \{ R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N(m_2), R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N(m_3) \}$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) \geq \min \{ R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N(m_2), R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N(m_3) \}$$

$$\geq \min \{ (-0.47, -0.31, -0.33), (-0.66, -0.46, -0.21) \} \geq (-0.66, -0.46, -0.33)$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = (-0.61, -0.44, -0.29) \geq (-0.66, -0.46, -0.33) \text{ it satisfies the second condition of N-Cubic Picture}$$

fuzzy linear space. But from example 3.2 $(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)$ is not interval valued N-Pythagorean fuzzy linear space.

Therefore, P-union is not a N-Cubic Picture fuzzy linear space.

ii) Consider interval valued N-Picture fuzzy linear spaces $J_{PF_1}^N$ and $J_{PF_2}^N$ as in Table 2 and Table 3.

Take the union of interval valued N-Picture fuzzy linear spaces we have

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = [-0.06, -0.04], [-0.29, -0.18], [-0.08, -0.03]$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2) = [-0.04, -0.03], [-0.15, -0.08] [-0.05, -0.02]$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) = [-0.06, -0.03], [-0.06, -0.05] [-0.07, -0.03]$$

We have $J_{IPF_1}^N \cup J_{IPF_2}^N$ is an interval valued N-Picture fuzzy set in \mathcal{I}

For $m_1 = m_2 * m_3$ and $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$ in definition 3.3

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2 * m_3) \leq \max \{ (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2), (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) \}$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) \leq \max \{ (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2), (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) \}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \max\{([-0.04, -0.03], [-0.15, -0.08], [-0.05, -0.02]), \\ &([-0.06, -0.03], [-0.06, -0.05], [-0.07, -0.03])\} \\ &\leq ([-0.04, -0.03], [-0.15, -0.08], [-0.05, -0.02]) \\ &(J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = ([-0.06, -0.04], [-0.29, -0.18], [-0.08, -0.03]) \\ &\leq ([-0.04, -0.03], [-0.15, -0.08], [-0.05, -0.02]) \end{aligned}$$

It is sensical, but from example 3.3 $R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N$ is not a N-Picture Fuzzy linear space.

Hence, P-intersection need not be a N-Cubic Picture Fuzzy linear space.

Internal and External N-Cubic Picture Fuzzy Linear Spaces

Definition 4.1 :

Suppose \mathcal{L} be a linear space over the field F . N-Cubic Picture fuzzy set is said to be $C_{PF}^N = (J_{PF}^N, R_{PF}^N)$ an Internal N-Cubic Picture fuzzy linear space abbreviated as INCPFLS if

$$J_{PF}^{N-}(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3) \leq R_{PF}^N(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3) \leq J_{PF}^{N+}(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3) \quad \forall$$

$m_1, m_2, m_3 \in L$ and $\xi, \gamma, \delta \in F$.

Example 4.1 : Consider \mathcal{L} be a linear space over the field F with the binary operation $*$ as in the example 3.1

Taking values of interval valued N-Picture fuzzy linear space J_{PF}^N as

$$J_{PF}^N(m_1) = [-0.32, -0.20], [-0.51, -0.40], [-0.40, -0.29]$$

$$J_{PF}^N(m_2) = [-0.57, -0.28], [-0.65, -0.22], [-0.31, -0.10]$$

$$J_{PF}^N(m_3) = [-0.48, -0.27], [-0.32, -0.18], [-0.19, -0.10]$$

Take values of N-Picture fuzzy linear space

$$R_{PF}^N(m_1) = (-0.27, -0.45, -0.35)$$

$$R_{PF}^N(m_2) = (-0.50, -0.36, -0.23)$$

$$R_{PF}^N(m_3) = (-0.42, -0.26, -0.17)$$

For $m_1 = m_2 * m_3$ and $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$ in definition 4.1

$$J_{PF}^{N-}(m_2 * m_3) \leq R_{PF}^N(m_2 * m_3) \leq J_{PF}^{N+}(m_2 * m_3)$$

$$J_{PF}^{N-}(m_1) \leq R_{PF}^N(m_1) \leq J_{PF}^{N+}(m_1)$$

$$-0.27 \in [-0.32, -0.20], -0.45 \in [-0.51, -0.40], -0.35 \in [-0.40, -0.29]$$

Hence, $C_{PF}^N = (J_{PF}^N, R_{PF}^N)$ is an interval valued N-Picture fuzzy linear space.

Definition 4.2 :

Let \mathcal{L} be a linear space over the field F . N-Cubic Picture fuzzy set is said to be $C_{PF}^N = (J_{PF}^N, R_{PF}^N)$ an External N-Cubic Picture fuzzy linear space abbreviated as ENCPFLS if

$$R_{PF}^N(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3) \notin (J_{PF}^{N-}(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3), J_{PF}^{N+}(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3)) \quad \forall m_1, m_2, m_3 \in L \text{ and } \xi, \gamma, \delta \in F.$$

Example 4.2 : Now, consider the values of interval valued N-Picture fuzzy set and N-Picture fuzzy set as presented in Table 2.

For $m_1 = m_2 * m_3$ and $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$ in definition 4.2

$$R_{PF}^N(m_2 * m_3) \notin (J_{PF}^{N-}(m_2 * m_3), J_{PF}^{N+}(m_2 * m_3))$$

$$R_{PF}^N(m_1) \notin (J_{PF}^{N-}(m_1), J_{PF}^{N+}(m_1))$$

$$(-0.54, -0.34, -0.22) \notin ([-0.06, -0.04], [-0.29, -0.18], [-0.08, -0.03])$$

Hence, $C_{PF}^N = (J_{PF}^N, R_{PF}^N)$ is an External N-Picture fuzzy linear space.

Proposition 4.1 : Let $C_{PF_1 I}^N = (J_{PF_1}^N, R_{PF_1}^N)$ and $C_{PF_2 I}^N = (J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_2}^N)$ are two INCPFLS. Then their R-intersection $(C_{PF_1 I}^N \cap C_{PF_2 I}^N)_R = (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)$ is an INCPFLS.

Proof . Since $C_{PF_1 I}^N$ and $C_{PF_2 I}^N$ are INCPFLS in \mathcal{L} then we have

$$J_{PF_1}^{N-}(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3) \leq R_{PF_1}^N(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3) \leq J_{PF_1}^{N+}(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3)$$

$$J_{PF_2}^{N-}(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3) \leq R_{PF_2}^N(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3) \leq J_{PF_2}^{N+}(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3)$$

for all $\xi, \delta, \rho \in F$ and $m_1, m_2, m_3 \in \mathcal{L}$.

According to theorem 3.1, the union of IVNPFSL is again IVNPFSL and intersection of NPFLS is again NPFLS. We have

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)^-(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3) \leq R_{PF_1}^N(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3) \leq (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)^+(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3)$$

Therefore, $(C_{PF_1 I}^N \cap C_{PF_2 I}^N)_R = (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)$ is an INCPFLS.

Proposition 4.2 : suppose $C_{PF_1 E}^N = (J_{PF_1}^N, R_{PF_1}^N)$ and $C_{PF_2 E}^N = (J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_2}^N)$ are two ENCPFLS. Then their R-intersection $(C_{PF_1 E}^N \cap C_{PF_2 E}^N)_R = (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)$ is an ENCPFLS.

Proof . Consider $C_{PF_1 E}^N$ and $C_{PF_2 E}^N$ are two ENCPFLS in \mathcal{L} then

$$R_{PF_1}^N(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3) \notin (J_{PF_1}^{N-}(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3), J_{PF_1}^{N+}(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3))$$

$$R_{PF_2}^N(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3) \notin (J_{PF_2}^{N-}(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3), J_{PF_2}^{N+}(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3))$$

$\forall m_1, m_2, m_3 \in L$ and $\xi, \gamma, \delta \in F$.

According to theorem 3.1, the union of IVNPFSL is again IVNPFSL and intersection of NPFLS is again NPFLS.

We have

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3) \notin ((J_{PF_1}^{N-} \cup J_{PF_2}^{N-})(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3), (J_{PF_1}^{N+} \cup J_{PF_2}^{N+})(\xi m_1 * \delta m_2 * \rho m_3))$$

Hence, $(C_{PF_1 E}^N \cap C_{PF_2 E}^N)_R = (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)$ is an ENCPFLS.

Proposition 4.3 : Let $C_{PF_1 I}^N = (J_{PF_1}^N, R_{PF_1}^N)$ and $C_{PF_2 I}^N = (J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_2}^N)$ are two INCPFLS. Then their P-intersection $(C_{PF_1 I}^N \cap C_{PF_2 I}^N)_P = (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)$ need not be INCPFLS.

Proof . Let \mathcal{L} be a linear space over the field F with the binary operation $*$ as shown in the example 3.1.

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = ([-0.53, -0.37], [-0.47, -0.21], [-0.18, -0.10])$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2) = ((-0.65, -0.38], (-0.46, -0.20], [-0.25, -0.16])$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) = ([-0.46, -0.26], [-0.37, -0.15], [-0.12, -0.06])$$

We have $J_{IPF_1}^N \cup J_{IPF_2}^N$ is an interval valued N-Picture fuzzy set in \mathcal{L}

Table 4. IVNPF_S (J_{PF}^N) and NPFS (R_{PF}^N) values

\mathcal{L}	J_{PF}^N	R_{PF}^N
m_1	[-0.72, -0.41], [-0.54, -0.35], [-0.23, -0.11]	(-0.45, -0.39, -0.13)
m_2	[-0.75, -0.50], [-0.52, -0.24], [-0.37, -0.18]	(-0.51, -0.24, -0.20)
m_3	[-0.46, -0.26], [-0.37, -0.15], [-0.12, -0.06]	(-0.36, -0.27, -0.10)

Table 5. Values corresponding to IVNPF_S (J_{PF}^N) and NPFS (R_{PF}^N)

\mathcal{L}	J_{PF}^N	R_{PF}^N
m_1	[-0.53, -0.37], [-0.47, -0.21], [-0.18, -0.10]	(-0.48, -0.35, -0.16)
m_2	[-0.65, -0.38], [-0.46, -0.20], [-0.25, -0.16]	(-0.39, -0.20, -0.19)
m_3	[-0.61, -0.49], [-0.55, -0.37], [-0.33, -0.07]	(-0.60, -0.47, -0.28)

For $m_1 = m_2 * m_3$ and $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$ in definition 3.3

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2 * m_3) \leq \max\{(J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2), (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_3)\}$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) \leq \max\{(J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2), (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_3)\}$$

$$\leq \max\{([-0.65, -0.38], [-0.46, -0.20] [-0.25, -0.16]),$$

$$([-0.46, -0.26], [-0.37, -0.15], [-0.12, -0.06])\}$$

$$\leq ([-0.46, -0.26], [-0.37, -0.15], [-0.12, -0.06])$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = ([-0.53, -0.37], [-0.47, -0.21] [-0.18, -0.10]) \leq ([-0.46, -0.26], [-0.37, -0.15], [-0.12, -0.06])$$

Which is correct. Now consider two N-Picture fuzzy sets $R_{PF_1}^N$ and $R_{PF_2}^N$ as defined in the above tables (Tables 4 and 5).

As $R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N$ is N-Picture fuzzy set

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = (-0.45, -0.35, -0.13)$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_2) = (-0.39, -0.20, -0.19)$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) = (-0.36, -0.27, -0.10)$$

We note that $(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)$ is N-Picture fuzzy set in \mathcal{L} For $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$ in definition 4.1.

$$J_{PF}^{N-}(m_2 * m_3) \leq R_{PF}^N(m_2 * m_3) \leq J_{PF}^{N+}(m_2 * m_3)$$

$$J_{PF}^{N-}(m_1) \leq R_{PF}^N(m_1) \leq J_{PF}^{N+}(m_1)$$

Here $-0.45 \in [-0.72, -0.41], -0.39 \in [-0.54, -0.25], -0.13 \in [-0.23, -0.11],$

For $m_1 = m_2 * m_3$ and $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$ in definition 3.3.

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_2 * m_3) \geq \min\{R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N(m_2), R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N(m_3)\}$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) \geq \min\{R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N(m_2), R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N(m_3)\}$$

$$\geq \min\{(-0.39, -0.20, -0.19), (-0.36, -0.27, -0.10)\}$$

$$\geq (-0.39, -0.27, -0.19)$$

$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = (-0.45, -0.35, -0.13) \geq (-0.39, -0.27, -0.19)$ it is inappropriate

Therefore, P-intersection of N-Cubic Picture fuzzy linear space need not be N-Cubic Picture fuzzy linear space.

Proposition 4.4 : Let $C_{PF_1}^N = (J_{PF_1}^N, R_{PF_1}^N)$ and $C_{PF_2}^N = (J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_2}^N)$ are two INCPFLS. Then their P-union

$(C_{PF_1}^N \cup C_{PF_2}^N)_P = (J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)$ need not be INCPFLS.

Proof. Now, consider the values of interval valued N-Picture fuzzy linear space and N - Picture fuzzy linear space as indicated in the Table 4 and also values mentioned in the Table 6.

Table 6. Values of IVNPFS (J_{PF}^N) and NPFS (R_{PF}^N).

\mathcal{X}	J_{PF}^N	R_{PF}^N
m_1	$[-0.56, -0.39], [-0.49, -0.33], [-0.27, -0.19]$	$(-0.40, -0.33, -0.23)$
m_2	$[-0.65, -0.45], [-0.57, -0.29], [-0.12, -0.03]$	$(-0.47, -0.29, -0.02)$
m_3	$[-0.36, -0.22], [-0.27, -0.13], [-0.23, -0.04]$	$(-0.25, -0.18, -0.15)$

$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = ([-0.72, -0.41], [-0.54, -0.35], [-0.27, -0.19])$

$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2) = ([-0.75, -0.50], [-0.57, -0.29], [-0.37, -0.18])$

$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) = ([-0.46, -0.26], [-0.37, -0.15], [-0.23, -0.14])$

We have $J_{IPF_1}^N \cap J_{IPF_2}^N$ is an interval valued fuzzy set in \mathcal{L} .

For $m_1 = m_2 * m_3$ and $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$ in definition 3.3

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2 * m_3) \leq \max\{(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2), (J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_3)\}$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) \leq \max\{(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2), (J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_3)\}$$

$$\leq \max\{([-0.75, -0.50], [-0.57, -0.29], [-0.37, -0.18]),$$

$$[-0.46, -0.26], [-0.37, -0.15], [-0.23, -0.14])\}$$

$$\leq ([-0.46, -0.26], [-0.37, -0.15], [-0.23, -0.14])$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = ([-0.72, -0.41], [-0.54, -0.35], [-0.27, -0.19]) \leq$$

$$([-0.46, -0.26], [-0.37, -0.15], [-0.23, -0.14])$$

It is appropriate.

Take two N-Picture fuzzy sets $R_{PF_1}^N$ and $R_{PF_2}^N$ as defined in the above tables

As $R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N$ is N-Picture fuzzy set

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = (-0.45, -0.39, -0.23)$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)(m_2) = (-0.51, -0.29, -0.02)$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) = (-0.36, -0.27, -0.15)$$

We note that $(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)$ is N-Picture fuzzy set in \mathcal{L}

For $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$ in definition 4.1

$$J_{PF}^{N-}(m_2 * m_3) \leq R_{PF}^N(m_2 * m_3) \leq J_{PF}^{N+}(m_2 * m_3)$$

$$J_{PF}^{N-}(m_1) \leq R_{PF}^N(m_1) \leq J_{PF}^{N+}(m_1)$$

Here $-0.40 \in [-0.56, -0.39], -0.33 \in [-0.49, -0.33], -0.23 \in [-0.27, -0.19],$

For $m_1 = m_2 * m_3$ and $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$ in definition 3.3

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)(m_2 * m_3) \geq \min\{R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N(m_2), R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N(m_3)\}$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) \geq \min\{R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N(m_2), R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N(m_3)\}$$

$$\geq \min\{(-0.51, -0.29, -0.02), (-0.36, -0.27, -0.15)\}$$

$$\geq (-0.51, -0.29, -0.15)$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = (-0.45, -0.39, -0.23) \geq (-0.51, -0.29, -0.15) \text{ it is inappropriate.}$$

Therefore, it is not necessary for P-union of two INCPFLS to be INCPFLS.

Proposition 4.5 : Let $C_{PF_1}^N = (J_{PF_1}^N, R_{PF_1}^N)$ and $C_{PF_2}^N = (J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_2}^N)$ are two INCPFLS. Then their R-union $(C_{PF_1}^N \cup C_{PF_2}^N)_R = (J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)$ need not be INCPFLS.

Proof. Now consider the values of interval valued N-Picture fuzzy linear space and N - Picture fuzzy linear space as presented in the Table 5 and also values listed below mentioned Table 7.

Table 7. Values pertaining to IVNPFS (J_{PF}^N) and NPFS (R_{PF}^N)

\mathcal{X}	J_{PF}^N	R_{PF}^N
m_1	[-0.35, -0.28], [-0.25, -0.17], [-0.16, -0.07]	(-0.29, -0.18, -0.09)
m_2	[-0.54, -0.30], [-0.59, -0.40], [-0.37, -0.03]	(-0.43, -0.51, -0.34)
m_3	[-0.67, -0.55], [-0.49, -0.26], [-0.47, -0.27]	(-0.58, -0.33, -0.42)

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = ([-0.53, -0.37], [-0.47, -0.21] [-0.18, -0.10])$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2) = ([-0.65, -0.38], [-0.59, -0.40] [-0.37, -0.23])$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) = ([-0.67, -0.55], [-0.55, -0.37] [-0.47, -0.27])$$

We have $J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N$ is an interval valued fuzzy set in \mathcal{X}
 For $m_1 = m_2 * m_3$ and $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$ in definition 3.3.

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2 * m_3) \leq \max\{(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2), (J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_3)\}$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) \leq \max\{(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2), (J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_3)\}$$

$$\leq \max\{([-0.65, -0.38], [-0.59, -0.40] [-0.37, -0.23]),$$

$$[-0.67, -0.55], [-0.55, -0.37] [-0.47, -0.27])\}$$

$$\leq ([-0.65, -0.38], [-0.55, -0.37] [-0.37, -0.23])$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = ([-0.53, -0.37], [-0.47, -0.21] [-0.18, -0.10])$$

$\leq ([-0.65, -0.38], [-0.55, -0.37] [-0.37, -0.23])$. It is inappropriate.

Choose two N-Picture fuzzy sets $R_{PF_1}^N$ and $R_{PF_2}^N$ as defined in the above tables.

As $R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N$ is N-Picture fuzzy set

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = (-0.29, -0.18, -0.09)$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_2) = (-0.39, -0.20, -0.19)$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) = (-0.58, -0.33, -0.28)$$

We note that $(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)$ is N-Picture fuzzy set in \mathcal{X}

For $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$ in definition 4.1

$$J_{PF}^{N-}(m_2 * m_3) \leq R_{PF}^N(m_2 * m_3) \leq J_{PF}^{N+}(m_2 * m_3)$$

$$J_{PF}^{N-}(m_1) \leq R_{PF}^N(m_1) \leq J_{PF}^{N+}(m_1)$$

Here $-0.29 \in [-0.35, -0.28], -0.18 \in [-0.25, -0.17], -0.09 \in [-0.16, -0.07]$,

For $m_1 = m_2 * m_3$ and $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$ in definition 3.3

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_2 * m_3) \geq \min\{R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N(m_2), R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N(m_3)\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & (R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) \geq \min\{R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N(m_2), R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N(m_3)\} \\ & \geq \min\{(-0.39, -0.20, -0.19), (-0.58, -0.33, -0.28)\} \\ & \geq (-0.58, -0.33, -0.28) \\ & (R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = (-0.29, -0.18, -0.09) \geq (-0.58, -0.33, -0.28) \end{aligned}$$

It is correct. Hence, R-Union of two INCPFLS need not be INCPFLS.

Proposition 4.6 : Let $C_{PF_1E}^N = (J_{PF_1}^N, R_{PF_1}^N)$ and $C_{PF_2E}^N = (J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_2}^N)$ are two ENCPFLS. Then their P-intersection $(C_{PF_1E}^N \cap C_{PF_2E}^N)_P = (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)$ need not be ENCPFLS.

Proof . With the binary operation $*$ as shown in the example 3.1, Let \mathcal{L} be a linear space over the field F .

Table 8. IVNPFS (J_{PF}^N) and NPFS (R_{PF}^N) values

\mathcal{L}	J_{PF}^N	R_{PF}^N
m_1	[-0.42, -0.30], [-0.37, -0.25], [-0.25, -0.17]	(-0.45, -0.40, -0.15)
m_2	[-0.59, -0.47], [-0.39, -0.23], [-0.25, -0.14]	(-0.30, -0.12, -0.09)
m_3	[-0.35, -0.21], [-0.22, -0.12], [-0.18, -0.08]	(-0.19, -0.27, -0.02)

Table 9. Values corresponding to IVNPFS (J_{PF}^N) and NPFS (R_{PF}^N)

\mathcal{L}	J_{PF}^N	R_{PF}^N
m_1	[-0.39, -0.22], [-0.27, -0.17], [-0.23, -0.13]	(-0.42, -0.30, -0.26)
m_2	[-0.50, -0.32], [-0.40, -0.27], [-0.20, -0.12]	(-0.35, -0.17, -0.11)
m_3	[-0.41, -0.31], [-0.28, -0.18], [-0.21, -0.15]	(-0.45, -0.31, -0.10)

$$\begin{aligned} & (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = ([-0.39, -0.22], [-0.27, -0.17], [-0.23, -0.13]) \\ & (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2) = ((-0.50, -0.32], (-0.39, -0.23], [-0.20, -0.12]) \\ & (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) = ([-0.35, -0.21], [-0.22, -0.12], [-0.18, -0.08]) \end{aligned}$$

We have $J_{IPF_1}^N \cup J_{IPF_2}^N$ is an interval valued N-Picture fuzzy set in \mathcal{L} .

For $m_1 = m_2 * m_3$ and $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$ in definition 3.3.

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2 * m_3) \leq \max\{(J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2), (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_3)\}$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) \leq \max\{(J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2), (J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_3)\}$$

$$\leq \max\{((-0.50, -0.32], (-0.39, -0.23], [-0.20, -0.12]),$$

$$([-0.35, -0.21], [-0.22, -0.12], [-0.18, -0.08])\}$$

$$\leq ([-0.35, -0.21], [-0.22, -0.12], [-0.18, -0.08])$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cup J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = ([-0.39, -0.22], [-0.27, -0.17], [-0.23, -0.13])$$

$\leq ([-0.35, -0.21], [-0.22, -0.12], [-0.18, -0.08])$ which is correct.

Now, consider two N-Picture fuzzy sets $R_{PF_1}^N$ and $R_{PF_2}^N$ as defined in the above Tables 8 and 9.

As $R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N$ is N-Picture fuzzy set

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = (-0.42, -0.30, -0.15)$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_2) = (-0.30, -0.12, -0.09)$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) = (-0.19, -0.27, -0.02)$$

We note that $(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)$ is N-Picture fuzzy set in \mathcal{L} .

For $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$ in definition 4.2.

$$R_{PF}^N(m_2 * m_3) \notin (J_{PF}^{N-}(m_2 * m_3), J_{PF}^{N+}(m_2 * m_3))$$

$$R_{PF}^N(m_1) \notin (J_{PF}^{N-}(m_1), J_{PF}^{N+}(m_1))$$

Here $-0.45 \notin [-0.42, -0.30], -0.40 \notin [-0.37, -0.25], -0.15 \notin [-0.25, -0.17]$,

For $m_1 = m_2 * m_3$ and $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$ in definition 3.3

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_2 * m_3) \geq \min \{R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N(m_2), R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N(m_3)\}$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) \geq \min \{R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N(m_2), R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N(m_3)\}$$

$$\geq \min \{(-0.30, -0.12, -0.09), (-0.19, -0.27, -0.02)\}$$

$$\geq (-0.30, -0.27, -0.09)$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = (-0.42, -0.30, -0.15) \geq (-0.30, -0.27, -0.09)$$

It is inappropriate. For this reason, it is not necessary for the P-intersection of two External N-Cubic Picture fuzzy linear spaces (ENCPFLS) to be External N-Cubic Picture fuzzy linear spaces (ENCPFLS).

Proposition 4.7 : Let $C_{PF_1}^N = (J_{PF_1}^N, R_{PF_1}^N)$ and $C_{PF_2}^N = (J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_2}^N)$ are two ENCPFLS. Then their P-union $(C_{PF_1}^N \cup C_{PF_2}^N)_P = (J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)$ need not be ENCPFLS.

Proof. Now consider the values of interval valued N-Picture fuzzy linear space and N - Picture fuzzy linear space as presented in the table8 and also values mentioned in the following Table 10.

Table 10. Values of IVNPFS (J_{PF}^N) and NPFS (R_{PF}^N)

\mathcal{L}	J_{PF}^N	R_{PF}^N
m_1	[-0.56, -0.41], [-0.27, -0.18], [-0.39, -0.26]	(-0.37, -0.31, -0.22)
m_2	[-0.45, -0.31], [-0.32, -0.20], [-0.19, -0.08]	(-0.27, -0.18, -0.01)
m_3	[-0.39, -0.29], [-0.17, -0.10], [-0.26, -0.16]	(-0.22, -0.31, -0.13)

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = ([-0.56, -0.41], [-0.37, -0.25] [-0.39, -0.26])$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2) = ([-0.59, -0.47], [-0.39, -0.23] [-0.25, -0.14])$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) = ([-0.39, -0.29], [-0.22, -0.12] [-0.26, -0.16])$$

We have $J_{IPF_1}^N \cap J_{IPF_2}^N$ is an interval valued fuzzy set in \mathcal{L} .

For $m_1 = m_2 * m_3$ and $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$ in definition 3.3

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2 * m_3) \leq \max \{ (J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2), (J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) \}$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) \leq \max \{ (J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2), (J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) \}$$

$$\leq \max \{ ([-0.59, -0.47], [-0.39, -0.23] [-0.25, -0.14]),$$

$$[-0.39, -0.29], [-0.22, -0.12] [-0.26, -0.16]) \}$$

$$\leq ([-0.39, -0.29], [-0.22, -0.12] [-0.25, -0.14])$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = ([-0.56, -0.41], [-0.37, -0.25] [-0.39, -0.26])$$

$$\leq ([-0.39, -0.29], [-0.22, -0.12] [-0.25, -0.14])$$

It is appropriate.

Consider two N-Picture fuzzy sets $R_{PF_1}^N$ and $R_{PF_2}^N$ as defined in the above tables

As $R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N$ is N-Picture fuzzy set

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = (-0.45, -0.40, -0.22)$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)(m_2) = (-0.30, -0.18, -0.09)$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) = (-0.22, -0.31, -0.13)$$

We note that $(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)$ is N-Picture fuzzy set in \mathcal{L} .

For $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$ in definition 4.2

$$R_{PF}^N(m_2 * m_3) \in (J_{PF}^{N-}(m_2 * m_3), J_{PF}^{N+}(m_2 * m_3))$$

$$R_{PF}^N(m_1) \in (J_{PF}^{N-}(m_1), J_{PF}^{N+}(m_1))$$

Here $-0.37 \in [-0.56, -0.41], -0.33 \in [-0.49, -0.33], -0.23 \in [-0.27, -0.19]$,

For $m_1 = m_2 * m_3$ and $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$ in definition 3.3

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)(m_2 * m_3) \geq \min \{ R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N(m_2), R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N(m_3) \}$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) \geq \min \{ R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N(m_2), R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N(m_3) \}$$

$$\geq \min \{ (-0.30, -0.18, -0.09), (-0.22, -0.31, -0.13) \}$$

$$\geq (-0.30, -0.31, -0.13)$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cap R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = (-0.45, -0.40, -0.22) \geq (-0.30, -0.31, -0.13) \text{ it is not correct.}$$

Hence, P-union of two ENCPFLS need not be ENCPFLS.

Proposition 4.8 : Let $C_{PF_1}^N = (J_{PF_1}^N, R_{PF_1}^N)$ and $C_{PF_2}^N = (J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_2}^N)$ are two ENCPFLS. Then their R-union $(C_{PF_1}^N \cup C_{PF_2}^N)_R = (J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N, R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)$ need not be ENCPFLS.

Now, consider the values of interval valued N-Picture fuzzy linear space and N - Picture fuzzy linear space as indicated in the Table 9 and also values given below Table 11.

Table 11. Values pertaining to IVNPFS (J_{PF}^N) and NPFS (R_{PF}^N)

\mathcal{L}	J_{PF}^N	R_{PF}^N
m_1	[-0.50, -0.41], [-0.45, -0.35], [-0.31, -0.23]	(-0.52, -0.32, -0.16)
m_2	[-0.44, -0.31], [-0.27, -0.16], [-0.17, -0.04]	(-0.27, -0.33, -0.21)
m_3	[-0.31, -0.18], [-0.17, -0.10], [-0.29, -0.19]	(-0.37, -0.28, -0.07)

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = ([-0.50, -0.41], [-0.45, -0.35] [-0.31, -0.23])$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2) = ([-0.50, -0.32], [-0.40, -0.27] [-0.20, -0.12])$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) = ([-0.41, -0.31], [-0.28, -0.18] [-0.29, -0.19])$$

We have $J_{IPF_1}^N \cap J_{IPF_2}^N$ is an interval valued fuzzy set in \mathcal{L} .

For $m_1 = m_2 * m_3$ and $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$ in definition 3.3

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2 * m_3) \leq \max \{ (J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2), (J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) \}$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) \leq \max \{ (J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_2), (J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) \}$$

$$\leq \max \{ ([-0.50, -0.32], [-0.40, -0.27] [-0.20, -0.12]),$$

$$[-0.41, -0.31], [-0.28, -0.18] [-0.29, -0.19]) \}$$

$$\leq ([-0.41, -0.31], [-0.28, -0.18] [-0.20, -0.12])$$

$$(J_{PF_1}^N \cap J_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = ([-0.50, -0.41], [-0.45, -0.35] [-0.31, -0.23])$$

\leq $([-0.41, -0.31], [-0.28, -0.18] [-0.29, -0.19])$ It is appropriate.

Choose two N-Picture fuzzy sets $R_{PF_1}^N$ and $R_{PF_2}^N$ as defined in the above tables

As $R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N$ is N-Picture fuzzy set

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = (-0.42, -0.30, -0.16)$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_2) = (-0.27, -0.17, -0.11)$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_3) = (-0.37, -0.28, -0.07)$$

We note that $(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)$ is N-Picture fuzzy set in \mathcal{L} .

For $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$ in definition 4.2

$$R_{PF}^N(m_2 * m_3) \notin (J_{PF}^{N-}(m_2 * m_3), J_{PF}^{N+}(m_2 * m_3))$$

$$R_{PF}^N(m_1) \notin (J_{PF}^{N-}(m_1), J_{PF}^{N+}(m_1))$$

Here $-0.52 \notin [-0.50, -0.41], -0.32 \notin [-0.45, -0.35], -0.16 \notin [-0.31, -0.23]$,

For $m_1 = m_2 * m_3$ and $\xi = 0, \delta = \rho = 1$ in definition 3.3

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_2 * m_3) \geq \min \{R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N(m_2), R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N(m_3)\}$$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) \geq \min \{R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N(m_2), R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N(m_3)\}$$

$\geq \min\{(-0.27, -0.17, -0.11), (-0.37, -0.28, -0.07)\}$

$\geq (-0.37, -0.28, -0.11)$

$$(R_{PF_1}^N \cup R_{PF_2}^N)(m_1) = (-0.42, -0.30, -0.16) \geq (-0.37, -0.28, -0.11)$$

It is not true. Hence, R-Union of two ENCPFLS does not necessarily have to be ENCPFLS.

4 Conclusion

In this study, we have applied N-cubic sets to N-Picture Fuzzy sets and further extended this concept to linear spaces in order to get N-cubic picture fuzzy linear spaces. It has been developed on the basis of interval valued N-Picture fuzzy linear spaces (IVNPFLS) and N-Picture fuzzy linear spaces (NPFLS) which addresses the adverse aspects of some issues, such as medication side effects. It also examines the fundamental operations such as P-union, P-intersection, R-union and R-intersection of N-Cubic Picture Fuzzy Linear Spaces. Furthermore, the notion of INCPFLS and ENCPFLS are discussed and P-union, P-intersection, R-union and R-intersection operations studied in detail with few examples. In future scope of research work, different aggregation operators can be studied with N-Cubic Picture Fuzzy Linear Spaces. Moreover, it would be extendable for decision-making solving problems on these linear spaces.

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